

Multi-DoF Time Domain Passivity Approach Based Drift Compensation for Telemanipulation

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Abstract—Despite being able to ensure passivity of teleoperation systems, Time Domain Passivity Approach (TDPA), causes an undesired effect, namely position drift. Although previous works focused on developing TDPA-based drift compensation methods to solve this issue, no multi-DoF treatment has been addressed. In that scope, this paper focuses on providing an extension of previous TDPA-based approaches to multi-DoF Cartesian-space teleoperation by exploring the Euclidean group of rigid body motions and the exponential map that relates it to its Lie algebra. The applicability of the proposed method to multi-DoF devices is validated through numerical simulation with round-trip time delays of 700 ms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Time Domain Passivity Approach (TDPA, [1]) is a widely used technique to passivate robotic teleoperation systems in the presence of communication delays and package loss. In spite of being able to render the communication channel passive, TDPA presents the drawback of creating position drift between master and slave devices whenever the passivity observer and passivity controller (PO-PC) pair is applied in admittance configuration. In order to tackle this issue, a few TDPA-based drift compensators were developed (e.g. [2]). Those approaches slightly modify the original TDPA formulation by adding a virtual velocity injection source before the PO-PC in order to compensate for the generated drift. The efficacy of TDPA-based compensation methods was demonstrated through their application to one-degree-of-freedom (1-DoF) devices or in a concatenated manner, treating each DoF as an independent system. Nevertheless, no Cartesian-space application of those compensators has been tackled to this date. In light of that, this paper aims at providing an extension of the previously presented drift compensators to the Cartesian space of multi-DoF robotic systems. This is achieved by defining the accumulated drift as an element of the Euclidean Lie group $SE(3)$ and defining the velocity injection law in order to regulate this value to the identity element, whenever allowed by the passivity condition. It is shown that, if allowed by the passivity condition, the presented method is able to successfully reduce the accumulated drift in TDPA. Teleoperation of the dynamic model of a Suspended Aerial Manipulator (SAM, [3]) is simulated to validate the proposed method.

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Fig. 1: Slave side of a P-F architecture. The PO-PC pair (β) is applied in admittance configuration. V_{ad} is the drift compensator velocity.

II. TIME DOMAIN PASSIVITY APPROACH

One of the most common teleoperation schemes is the position force (P-F) architecture [1], where the master velocity is sent through the channel and serves as desired velocity to the slave. In turn, the force produced by the slave-side controller is sent back to the master. Using a hybrid of circuit and network representation, the slave side of the TDPA-passivated P-F architecture can be represented as shown in Fig. 1. There, the communication channel is represented by a Time Delay Power Network (TDPN, [1]). V_m and V_s are the velocities of the master and slave devices. F_s is the force exerted by the slave-side controller and \hat{F}_m is its delayed version applied to the master device. β and V_{ad} are the admittance-type passivity controller and the drift compensation velocity source. \tilde{V}_{sd} is the delayed master velocity and V_{sd} is the velocity given as a reference to the slave controller.

In order to enforce the passivity of the channel, i.e. $E_{out}^S(k) \leq E_{in}^M(k) \forall k$, the passivity controller removes part of the velocity given as a reference to the slave robot as

$$V_{sd}(k) = \tilde{V}_{sd}(k) - V_{pc}(k), \quad (1)$$

where $V_{pc}(k) = \beta(k)F_s(k)$.

III. MULTI-DOF DRIFT COMPENSATOR

A. Notations and Definitions

1) *The Special Euclidean group and its Lie algebra:* The pose of a rigid body in space can be represented by the special Euclidean Lie group $SE(3)$. Furthermore, the velocity of a rigid body can be expressed by elements of the Lie algebra of $SE(3)$, namely $\mathfrak{se}(3)$, as $[V]^\wedge = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\omega} & v \\ \mathbf{0} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathfrak{se}(3)$, where $\hat{\cdot}$ indicates the skew-symmetric operator applied to a vector in \mathbb{R}^3 , and $\omega, v \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are angular and linear velocities,

respectively. Adding to that, due to the isomorphism between $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ and \mathbb{R}^6 , it is useful to define the operator $[\cdot]^\wedge : \mathbb{R}^6 \rightarrow \mathfrak{se}(3)$, such that the velocity of a rigid body can be expressed as a vector in \mathbb{R}^6 , which can be represented in body (${}^B\mathbf{V}$) or in spatial frame (${}^S\mathbf{V}$) [4].

B. Representation of Drift in $SE(3)$

Assuming the teleoperation task comprises the complete Cartesian space, the velocities $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{sd}(k)$ and $\mathbf{V}_{sd}(k)$ can be defined to be *body velocities* [4] represented by vectors in \mathbb{R}^6 as ${}^{\mathcal{D}}\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{sd}(k) = [\omega_{\mathcal{D}}^T \ v_{\mathcal{D}}^T]^T$ and ${}^{\mathcal{D}}\mathbf{V}_{sd}(k) = [\omega_{\mathcal{D}}^T \ v_{\mathcal{D}}^T]^T$, where \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D} are the frames defined by the delayed master orientation and the orientation given to the slave as the reference, respectively. The discrete-time integral of ${}^{\mathcal{D}}\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{sd}$ and ${}^{\mathcal{D}}\mathbf{V}_{sd}$ can be computed as

$$\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{D}}(k) = \mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{D}}(k-1) \exp_{SE(3)}([\mathcal{D}\mathbf{V}_{sd}(k)]^\wedge \Delta T), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{D}}(k) = \mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{D}}(k-1) \exp_{SE(3)}([\mathcal{D}\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{sd}(k)]^\wedge \Delta T), \quad (3)$$

where $\exp_{SE(3)} : \mathfrak{se}(3) \rightarrow SE(3)$ is the exponential map from $\mathfrak{se}(3)$, the Lie algebra of $SE(3)$, onto $SE(3)$ itself [4], and ΔT is the sampling time. Using the definitions above, the drift present in the system at a given time step can be represented in $SE(3)$ by

$$\mathbf{g}_E(k) \triangleq \mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{D}}(k)^{-1} \mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{D}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_E(k) & \mathbf{p}_E(k) \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

It can be noted from (1)–(4) that, if the PC acts at a time step, it will affect the value of \mathbf{g}_E for all future time steps. In case \mathbf{g}_E is not the identity matrix, there will be a drift between the delayed master pose and the pose given as reference to the slave.

C. Cartesian-Space Drift Compensation

From Fig. 1, it can be seen that, when the drift compensator is added, (1) becomes

$$\mathbf{A}d_{\mathbf{g}_E}(k) {}^{\mathcal{D}}\mathbf{V}_{sd}(k) = {}^{\mathcal{D}}\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{sd}(k) + {}^{\mathcal{D}}\mathbf{V}_{ad}(k) - {}^{\mathcal{D}}\mathbf{V}_{pc}(k), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{A}d_{\mathbf{g}_E}(k)$ is defined as in [4]. In order to reduce the drift between master and slave devices whenever allowed by the aforementioned passivity conditions, the following law can be used

$$\omega_{ad}(k) = -\frac{1}{\Delta T} \mathbf{k}_R \boldsymbol{\varphi}_E(k-1), \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{ad}(k) = -\frac{1}{\Delta T} \mathbf{A}(\omega_{ad}(k)\Delta T)^{-T} \mathbf{K}_T \mathbf{p}_E(k-1),$$

$${}^{\mathcal{D}}\mathbf{V}_{ad}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{ad}(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_{ad}(k) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}}_E(k-1) = \log_{SO(3)}(\mathbf{R}_E(k-1))$ [4], and $\mathbf{K}_T \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and $\mathbf{k}_R \in \mathbb{R}$ are the translational and rotational gains of the compensator. Moreover, \mathbf{A}^{-T} is defined as in [4].

It can be verified that, whenever allowed to act by the passivity controller, if the gains are chosen such that $0 < \mathbf{k}_R < 2$ and $0 < \text{eig}(\mathbf{K}_T) < 2$, the proposed compensator ensures that

$$\|\boldsymbol{\varphi}_E(k)\| < \|\boldsymbol{\varphi}_E(k-1)\| \wedge \|\mathbf{p}_E(k)\| < \|\mathbf{p}_E(k-1)\|, \quad (8)$$

as long as $\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_E(k-1)) \neq 1$.

Fig. 2: Master and slave positions (left) and orientations (right), without drift compensation (top) and with drift compensation (bottom) – 700 ms round-trip delay.

IV. VALIDATION RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows master and slave position and orientation values during simulated bilateral teleoperation of the SAM [3] in the presence of time delay. The top and bottom figures show the results of TDPA-based teleoperation with and without the proposed drift compensator, respectively. It can be noted that the position and orientation drift that appeared during TDPA-only teleoperation was successfully compensated when the proposed approach was applied.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a TDPA-based drift-compensation approach, which is capable of compensating pose drift generated by the passivity controller. The method was conceived as an extension of previously presented approaches to multi-DoF robots by exploring characteristics of the $SE(3)$ group and the exponential map of its Lie algebra, $\mathfrak{se}(3)$.

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